

THE IDEALIZATION OF WOMEN IN EDGAR ALLAN POE’S POEMS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi Edgar Allan Poe she'riyatida ayollarni ideallashtirish mavzusi tahlil qilinadi. Tezisdagi Edgar Poning “Annabel Li,” “Lenore” va “Helen” she’rlarida ayol qahramonlarining go’zalligini ideallashtirishda romantizmga hos tarflanish uslublari ko’rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ideallashtirish, she'riyat, romantizm, tushkunlik muhiti, fojiali romantika.

Аннотация: Данный тезис посвящен идеализации женщин в поэзии Эдгара Аллана По. Благодаря анализу избранных стихотворений, в том числе «Аннабель Ли», «Ленор» и «Елене», тезис показывает, как По изображает женщин как неземных существ, часто романтизированных до крайней степени.

Ключевые слова: идеализация, поэзия, романтизм, меланхолическая атмосфера, трагический романс.

Abstract: This thesis focuses on the idealization of women in the poetry of Edgar Allan Poe. Through an analysis of selected poems, including “Annabel Lee,” “Lenore,” and “To Helen,” this thesis depicts how Poe portrays women as ethereal beings, often romanticized and idolized to an extreme degree.

Keywords: idealization, women, poetry, romanticism, melancholic atmosphere, tragic romance.

Introduction

Edgar Allan Poe stands out among American poets for his consistent focus on women as poetic subjects. Among the fifty-two poems undoubtedly attributed to him, twenty-five—comprising many of his finest works—center around women. These women often lend their names to the poems, such as “To Helen” (1831), “Lenore”

(1831), “Eulalie – A Song” (1845), and “Annabel Lee” (1849). Other poems follow a similar pattern, adopting titles like “To —” or “To F—,” with variations in line length and structure. While other poets have created numerous female characters, Poe's treatment of women remains distinctive. Unlike those who approach women as occasional subjects, Poe draws continual inspiration from them, reflecting his own personality to varying degrees. Although his prose tends to be more objective and less focused on women, certain stories reveal his enduring fascination with them. Poe's female characters often share physical and character traits, frequently described as possessing a “classic face” and “hyacinth hair,” alongside noble qualities and enduring love for the protagonist. Their names, carefully chosen for their musical quality, often feature the letter L, adding to the poems' melancholic atmosphere. The melancholic atmosphere with the letter L can be clearly seen in his “Annabel Lee,” “Lenore,” and “To Helen” poems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The idealization of women is a recurring motif in the poetry of Edgar Allan Poe, particularly evident in his notable works such as “Annabel Lee,” “Lenore,” and “To Helen.” In these poems, Poe constructs female characters who embody qualities of beauty, purity, and otherworldliness, elevating them to almost mythic proportions.

“**Annabel Lee**” stands as one of Poe's most renowned poems, portraying the titular character as a symbol of enduring love that transcends death itself. Annabel Lee is depicted as a figure of ethereal beauty and innocence, her memory immortalized in the speaker's lamentation of their tragic separation.

“**Lenore**” presents a female character whose name becomes synonymous with mourning and loss. Lenore is idealized as a haunting presence, her absence serving as the catalyst for the speaker's grief and longing. Through vivid imagery and melancholic verse, Poe romanticizes Lenore as a spectral figure whose memory haunts the narrative landscape.

“**To Helen**” showcases Poe's idealization of feminine beauty through the portrayal of Helen of Troy. Drawing inspiration from classical mythology, Poe portrays Helen as the epitome of physical and spiritual beauty, her image evoking feelings of

awe and admiration in the speaker. Through his depiction of Helen, Poe celebrates the timeless allure of feminine grace and charm.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Edgar Allan Poe's idealization of women serves to elevate them to a status of almost divine significance, imbuing them with qualities of purity, beauty, and eternal love. Through his evocative language and imagery, Poe invites readers to contemplate the transcendent power of feminine beauty and the enduring impact of love and loss. Influenced by his tragic personal life with the death of most of the women he ever cared about, Poe's poems revolve around the issue of coping with the loss of a loved one, and focus mainly on male narrators dealing with the death of their lover. Poe depicts beautiful women, praising their figures, but omits to acknowledge their personalities and moral features, transforming these women into bodies and objects. He writes mournful characters to try to deal with his own grief. Poe's entire career thus seems to revolve around the issue of the loss of the ideal woman and Poe's writing is his therapy. The author tries to cure his sorrow and to conquer the “fever called 'Living'” by discussing his wounds, using the best subject he could have imagined: “The death [...] of a beautiful woman is, unquestionably, the most poetic topic in the world – and equally is it beyond doubt that the lips best suited for such topic are those of a bereaved lover.”

CONCLUSION

In Edgar Allan Poe's poetry, the idealization of women serves as a recurring theme, reflecting the author's preoccupation with beauty, mortality, and the supernatural. Through his romanticized portrayal of female characters, Poe illustrates complex themes of love, loss, and longing, inviting readers to contemplate the nature of desire and the human condition. However, this idealization also raises questions about gender roles and agency within Poe's narratives, highlighting tensions between the idealized feminine and the realities of women's lives.

REFERECES:

1. A Source for "Annabel Lee" by Robert Adger Law The Journal of English and Germanic Philology , Apr., 1922, Vol. 21, No. 2
2. Kevin Reynaud. The Loss of the Ideal Woman in Edgar Allan Poe’s Poetry. Literature. 2013.
3. Poe, Edgar Allan. The Complete Poetry of Edgar Allan Poe. New York City: New American Library, 2008
4. Empric, Julienne H. A Note on 'Annabel Lee.' In: “Poe Studies,” Vol. 6, No.1.
5. Pullman: Washington State University Press, June 197
6. Richards, Eliza. Women's Place in Poe Studies. In: “Poe Studies/Dark Romanticism,” Vol. 33, No. 1-2. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers, 2000
7. Shanks, Edward. Edgar Allan Poe. London: MacMillan and Co., 1937